

ABSTRACT.

Gender-Based Violence (GBV) is a pervasive National Public Health challenge in Uganda with profound biological and psychological impacts, particularly among individuals living with Chronic Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs), as observed at GPC clinic, Kyamulibwa and according to research by (social Innovation Health Projects in Uganda 2025).

BACKGROUND. *In rural Uganda, where the burden of NCDs is increasing within structurally inequitable settings, increasing individual vulnerabilities, the intersection of GBV and chronic illness remains critically underexplored. This study aims to investigate the prevalence, lived experiences, and consequences of GBV among adults with NCDs as a reverse adversary in Kyamulibwa Sub-County, Kalungu District, leveraging on the General Population Cohort (GPC) in Kyamulibwa Sub-County, Kalungu District.*

PROBLEM STATEMENT. *Despite the documented effects of GBV, such as poor mental health, Non-adherence to treatment, and worsened disease outcomes, national and local policies rarely integrate GBV as a postdromal event into chronic NCD disease care frameworks. Preliminary GPC Clinic data, kyamulibwa, suggest that 60% of NCD patients report at least some form of GBV exposure, three times higher than the general clinic outpatient population. Yet, structured screening tools and systematic integration of GBV data remain absent, revealing a critical gap in policy, research, and practice.*

METHODOLOGY. *To explore this phenomenon, the study will adopt a mixed-methods cross-sectional design. Quantitative surveys will estimate GBV prevalence and examine associations with NCD types, while qualitative interviews will provide contextual depth into survivors' experiences, vulnerabilities, and coping mechanisms. The Intersectionality Framework, capturing interlocking influences of gender, health status, socioeconomic position, and cultural norms, guides the research.*

Ethical Consideration, *Clearance will be sought from MRC/UVRI and LSHTM Uganda Research Unit, Uganda Martyrs University and UVRI Research and Ethics Committee, to carry out a full research study.*

DATA ANALYSIS. *Data will be collected using validated tools Abuse Assessment Screen (AAS), the Composite Abuse Scale (CAS), and the WHO Quality of Life scale (WHOQOL-BREF). STATA ver.18 will be used to facilitate inferential statistical analysis; NVivo ver.14 will be employed for qualitative thematic coding. Joint displays will synthesize both data strands for integrated interpretation.*

SIGNIFICANCE. *Conducted in a resource-constrained rural setting marked by poverty, gender inequality, and limited healthcare infrastructure, the study aims to inform the integration of GBV screening into NCD care, shape equitable health policies, and promote survivor-centred, trauma-informed chronic disease management.*

Keywords. *Postdromal Gender Based Violence, Non-communicable diseases in rural Uganda, general population cohort.*